

Brown planthopper populations on resistant varieties treated with a resurgence-causing insecticide

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Previous laboratory and field experiments at IRRI have shown that the application of certain insecticides to susceptible rice varieties can induce resurgence of brown planthopper (BPH) populations. Because most Philippine farmers grow BPH-resistant varieties, we sought to determine if high BPH populations would develop on resistant varieties sprayed with a resurgence-causing insecticide. The varieties tested were IR20 (no gene for resistance); IR26 and IR29 (*Bph 1* gene); and IR32, IR36, IR40, and IR42 (*bph 2* gene). The entries were sprayed 7 times with cypermethrin in 300 liters water at 20 g a.i./ha. The BPH population was assessed twice a week by counting the BPH in 10 randomly selected hills/replication.

Biotypes 1 and 2 were predominant. The highest populations were on IR20 (susceptible to all biotypes), on IR29 and IR26 (susceptible to biotype 2) (see figure). All varieties with the *bph 2* gene, except IR40, had low populations. In previous field tests IR40 was less resistant to biotype 2 than IR32, IR36, and IR42. The study indicates that BPH populations remain low on varieties that are highly resistant to the prevailing biotype in spite of being sprayed with a resurgence-causing insecticide.

Brown planthopper populations on susceptible (IR20) and resistant varieties sprayed with a resurgence-inducing insecticide. IRRI, 1979.

Resurgence can be a serious problem for farmers when a biotype shifts and a previously resistant variety is rendered susceptible (this happened with IR26 in Indonesia and the Philippines). Although

this is speculation, we are concerned about the possibility that application of resurgence-causing insecticides could accelerate biotype selection on resistant varieties. ■

Soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica contents in leaf sheaths of rice varieties carrying different BPH-resistance genes

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In experiments to identify the chemical factors that influence varietal resistance to the brown planthopper (BPH), we found that soluble silicic acid, common in rice plants, strongly inhibits sucking by the BPH. Such inhibitory action was

effective at rates as low as 0.01 mg Si/ml. To test the assumption that soluble silicic acid might be involved in BPH resistance, we compared soluble and insoluble silica contents in the rice leaf sheaths of 28 varieties. Soluble silicic acid was extracted with 70% ethanol and measured colorimetrically by the molybdc acid method. Leaf sheaths after ethanol extraction were digested with a mixture of nitric acid, sulfuric acid, and 60% perchloric acid (5:1:2, vol/vol) for the analysis of insoluble silica. The residues were ashed in the

digested samples and the silica contents were weighed.

The absence of significant differences in contents of soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica among susceptible and resistant varieties (see table) indicates that silicic compounds do not influence BPH resistance. That was supported by evidence that the resistance level of Mudgo grown in a silica-free culture solution did not change. The silicic acid, usually distributed in the peripheral tissues outside the BPH phloem-sucking area, possibly influences phloem

localization by the insect, thus preventing an erroneous sap intake from parenchymal tissues. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Drought resistance

Studies on physiological aspects of drought in rice

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Different aspects of drought resistance in rice were studied in the field and greenhouse at IRRI.

The water-retention capacity at wilting stage of seedlings of different varieties ranged from 2 to 4.11 g/g dry matter. BR3 had the highest water-retention capacity and IR442, the lowest. Wilted seedlings of IR442 could hardly recover when watered.

When watered in the greenhouse 24 hours after wilting at the active tillering stage, the seedlings recovered from 32 to 72% of their length within 3 days. When watered 48 hours after wilting BR3 had the highest leaf-recovery efficiency and Katakara, the lowest. No variety recovered when watered 72 hours after wilting.

The wilting rates of rice varieties subjected to water stress developed by 1.5% NaCl at the active tillering stage varied widely.

When grown under prolonged desiccation in the field, BR3 gave the highest yield and Chandina the lowest. Root length development varied from 13 to 65 cm among varieties grown under moisture stress in polyvinyl chloride (PVC) pipes.

A variety's drought resistance may vary under different conditions. Drought tolerance and drought avoidance mechanisms may be functions of separate genes. For example, in the PVC-pipe experiment, IR26 had higher resistance in terms of leaf tolerance for wilting, but

Soluble silicic acid and insoluble silica contents in rice varieties carrying different BPH resistance genes. IRRI, 1979.

Gene	Variety	Soluble silicic acid (mg Si/wet g)	Insoluble silica ^a	
			mg SiO ₂ /dry g	mg SiO ₂ /wet g
No gene	IR8	0.121	94	10.7
	IR20	0.113	106	11.0
	IR22	0.128	113	12.8
	IR24	0.121	104	11.4
	TN1	0.125	100	11.3
<i>Bph 1</i>	IR26	0.116	114	10.5
	IR2058-78	0.110	100	13.4
	Mudgo	0.115	97	10.8
	CO 10	0.109	112	14.9
	MTU15	0.101	116	13.4
<i>bph 2</i>	IR32	0.127	115	13.0
	H5	0.118	96	8.8
	H105	0.118	107	11.0
	CR94-13	0.125	114	11.4
	ASD7	0.106	91	11.6
<i>Bph 3</i>	Kuruhondarwala	0.110	112	11.4
	Gangala	0.109	107	10.8
	Rathu Heenati	0.120	105	11.4
<i>bph 4</i>	Heenhoranamawee	0.124	91	9.8
	Babawee	0.109	105	9.3
	Lekam Samba	0.096	91	10.6
	Kalukuruwee	0.103	107	11.2
	Kahata Samba	0.121	102	9.6
Unknown gene	PTB21	0.107	98	13.0
	PTB33	0.119	124	13.5
	Sudu Hondarwala	0.116	100	11.9
	Sinna Sivappu	0.114	91	11.8
	Balamawee	0.113	102	11.6
	Av	0.115	104.3	11.5

^aIn leaf sheaths after ethanol extraction.

its roots developed poorly and its ratio of root to shoot length was low. Dular and Mala were moderately tolerant of leaf wilting, although their avoidance capacity was high, as shown by their deep

root systems and high root-to-shoot length ratios. Therefore, evaluation for these two drought-resistance mechanisms should be separate. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Deep water

Deepwater rice yields in Bangladesh

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Results of the first systematic assessment of Bangladesh deepwater rice yields in 1977 were described earlier (IRRN 35 October 1978). The study was continued in 1978.

Growth conditions for deepwater rice were generally favorable; inundation was later but more rapid, and water